

Title: Die Schönheit der Vergänglichkeit

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

The illustrated structure and the organization of lines and strokes are the essence of the Chinese calligraphy. In an artistic analog to musical expression, the rhythmic dynamics of the hand, the time-shifting method, the articulation of breath, the wet pen/dry nib and the speed of pen movement during the writing-process-momentum combine the characteristics of time and space in a distinctively individual and an immediately compositional way.

Here is the occasion to pick up the brush again for the desire of linking the beauty of the cultural treasure with the globally interconnected understanding of contemporary music.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Die Schönheit der Vergänglichkeit by Se-Lien Chuang & Andreas Weixler
interactive audiovisual improvisation for C²S² - Chinese Calligraphic Scenic Score

Duration: 6 min - 8 min

Instruments –

Se-Lien Chuang, interactive visuals, vocal & C²S²

Andreas Weixler, e-guitar & audio realtime processing

C²S² - Chinese Calligraphic Scenic Score -

The Chinese calligraphy will be written in Cursive script (草書) in realtime.
Every stroke can be interpreted musically.

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Scene 8 & 10 will be written/painting on-site in realtime.

Here the link for the 10 scenes of writing in varied time lapse video -

Each scene of the demos is within 2 min.

Scene 1-7 & scene 9 as described above.

Scene 8 & 10 are written on-site in realtime

Scene 1

如意 as one wishes

SSCC_4fachBeschleunigung (1 min 39 sec)

<https://youtu.be/aWvDSTFgPpo>

Scene 2

淡泊 indifferent

SSCC_8fachBeschleunigung (1 min)

https://youtu.be/gNM52-4_EME

Scene 3

風飛家 wind flying home

SSCC_8fachBeschleunigung (1 min 02 sec)

<https://youtu.be/beKB7oIZZtk>

Scene 4

飛龍在天 flying dragon in the sky

SSCC_8fachBeschleunigung (1 min 04 sec)

<https://youtu.be/lz7Wz5hO1X8>

Scene 5

精彩 wonderful

SSCC_8fachBeschleunigung (33 sec)

<https://youtu.be/XPweVNKnJ1g>

Scene 6

恬靜 quiet

SSCC_8fachBeschleunigung (1min 14 sec)

<https://youtu.be/ivFdZH3P51M>

Scene 7

天涯共此時 over the horizon of the nature together at this time

SSCC_8fachBeschleunigung (1min 31 sec)

<https://youtu.be/CGeRTqAi9pI>

Scene 8

comprovisation

SSCC_20fachBeschleunigung (1 min 18 sec)

<https://youtu.be/CJdOc2uZWIU>

Scene 9

Excerpt from

孟浩然 – 宿桐廬江寄廣陵舊遊

MENG Haoran – To Old Friends in Guangling on Mooring Overnight on the Tonglu River

山暝聽猿愁 listening to the ape's sorrow in the dark mountains

滄江急夜流 rapid night current in Cangjiang River

風鳴兩岸葉 the wind blowing the singing leaves on both sides of the shore

月照一孤舟 the moon shines on a lonely boat

demo - SSCC_20fachBeschleunigung (1min 57 sec)

<https://youtu.be/VD-VgVVTeic>

Scene 10

comprovisation

SSCC_20fachBeschleunigung (1min 57 sec)

<https://youtu.be/VtzqgsYGILE>

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

On stage there will be projection of the interactive visuals of C³S²- Chinese Calligraphic Scenic Score for the audience.

Realtime audio processing of the scratch sound and the acoustic instruments: multi-channel granular synthesis, spectral delay, FFT filtering, ring modulation, spectral freeze verb in a joint performance of acoustic and electronic players.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video demo: <https://youtu.be/cdHGZsppDrI> (12 min 48 sec)

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ETHICAL STANDARDS

We will conduct our research in a way that respects the rights, dignity and well-being of our participants and other stakeholders.

REFERENCES

- [1] Se-Lien Chuang, Andreas Weixler, “Sonic Environment Daegu” in *International Computer Music Conference – ICMC 2018*, Daegu, 2018, 10th August 2018 Daegu Concert House, Grand Hall. excerpt <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J6WF6egQrgo>
- [2] Se-Lien Chuang, Andreas Weixler, “Sonic Environment Daegu” in *International Computer Music Conference – ICMC 2018*, Daegu, 2018, 10th August 2018 Daegu Concert House, Grand Hall. ICMA award best European performance 2018 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Si8lzY1FXuQ>